

Case Report

The New Face of the “Old Diseases” - A Case Report

P. Chakarova^{1*}, A. Vasileva¹, Iv. Chakarov², R. Marinov³

Abstract

¹Clinic of pediatrics, UMHAT “Prof. Dr. St. Kirkovich” Stara Zagora

²National Heart Hospital, UMHAT Sofia

³Clinic of childhood clinical hematology and oncology UMHAT “Tsaritsa Yoanna-ISUL” Sofia

*Corresponding Author's Email: ani_asken@abv.bg

In recent years, a number of well-known diseases that can safely be called "old diseases", well known in the clinical pediatrics are starting to show up with a rather atypical clinical picture. It is difficult to find the exact cause of this phenomenon. The most probable reason is the influence of exogenous factories - a severe pathogenicity of etiological factors (viruses, bacteria, parasites), but also of many environmental factors. What is more, the dramatic change in the genome of the individual and a change in immunogenicity requires a long period of time and solid evidence. In support of the highly debatable issues in the altered clinical picture, we present a clinical case with a manifestation of two nosological units with atypical, oligosymptomatic onset, but also with complications in clinical development that posed a serious risk to the patient's life. The first nosological unit is colonization in the CNS of a parasitic echinococcosis cyst, followed by the manifestation of a systemic form of rheumatoid arthritis. The complexities of success in diagnostic, clinical, and therapeutic behavior in this case are evidence of the need for a multi-team approach.

Keywords: CT, Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, Solitary echinococcal cyst, Therapy

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of premature occurrence or rejuvenation of the clinical manifestation of the illnesses during childhood is first referred to as diabetes mellitus. In recent years, many other diseases have begun to appear relatively early, far from the peak age. Moreover, what makes it extremely difficult to have an early diagnosis and timely treatment is the oligosymptomatic clinical picture, even its initiation and early demonstration of severe complications.

The logical question is why the so-called well-known "old diseases" have a new face? It is difficult to give the exact explanation because of the drastic changes in the genome and those in immunogenicity require for a long time. At the current stage, the most likely cause is the influence of the so-called exogenous factors - the severe pathogenicity of the etiological agents (viruses, bacteria, parasites), as well as the influence of environmental factors (Karlson and Deane, 2012).

In support of this debatable phenomenon, we present a clinical case with the manifestation of two nosological units with atypical oligosymptomatic onset, moreover developing complications that endangered the life of the patient.

The present clinical pathology in this patient is a serious trial for the clinician, requiring serious clinical experience, depth of diagnostic thinking, a wide range of differential diagnosis and multi-disciplinary team problem-solving.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is about a boy of 14 years, whose suffering has begun at the age of 7. The underlying clinical symptoms are extremely variable. Each new clinical symptom had even a more aggressive clinical manifestation without corre-

Figure 1. Native CT of the brain.

lating with the previous nosological unit.

The first disease has begun with a runny nose, cough, and fever. Due to the rapid deterioration of the general condition, the patient was hospitalized at the Clinic of Pediatrics Stara Zagora. The clinical status and radiograph of the lungs showed evidence of a bilateral pneumonic process. At day 6 of the treatment, a series of generalized tonic-clonic seizures, more pronounced on the right limbs and a loss of consciousness, were observed. For a short time, the condition recovered but the patient remained somnolent. The duration of the two seizures was around 40 seconds, with postictal sleep without losing control of the pelvic floor (pelvic incontinence). From the neurological status there were no signs of meninge-radicular irritation syndrome, but the cranial nerves showed right-sided paresis from a central type of the facial nerve. Besides, there were hyperreflexia and extended reflex zones, more pronounced in the right. The sample for latent paresis was positive for the right limbs. The performed native CAT revealed large cerebral hemisphere (LLCH) in the left, and in the front-tempo-parietal zone the presence of a large hypodense lesion with a circular shape, average density - 5-7 HU, with sharp outlines of 58 / 65.8 mm without perifocal edema (Ray et al., 2001). Figure 1.

The anterior horn of the left lateral ventricle is displaced to the right. The right lateral ventricle is dilated (Nanasis et al., 1999; Tuzun et al., 2004). Abdominal ultrasound: liver - slightly enlarged, but with normoechoic parenchyma and dilated vena cava I stage. After four days later, the patient's condition worsened: GCS 8 p. The right-sided hemiparesis turned to plegia, which consequently led to an emergency surgery - signs of the

echinococcal capsule (Mircevski, 1989; Papi and Khudale, 1998). Figure 2.

Successful removal and subsequent treatment with Zentel were performed. A control CT was made, showing the area of the operative intervention with clear margins, liquid-equivalent zone with axial dimensions of 23/36 mm (Figure 3).

Discrete traction of the ipsilateral ventricle, in the cerebral parenchyma supra- and infratemporal, no occupying spaces process, as well as structures or other focal pathological changes in the density, were found.

In October 2018, the patient has been admitted to the Clinic of Pediatrics with the following symptoms: fever, abdominal pain, upper dyspeptic and urethral syndromes. Several days before the hospitalization, he had had a pain behind the sternum with irradiation to the scapula and excretion of dark urine.

Patient's status from the admission - severe general condition, febrile, intoxicated. A heart rate of 100 beats/min, deaf heart tones, no pathological noises. Blood pressure 120/80 mmHg.

Laboratory tests: CRP 242.3 mg / l; CK-MB 19.3 U / l; Hemostasis profile: PT 58.1%; aPTT 29.5 sec.; fibrinogen 6.04 g / l; INR 1.42. Abdominal ultrasound - significantly enlarged liver with size in right MCL 157 mm, non-homogeneous parenchyma. Around the gall bladder there is a hypoechoic area of 15 mm in size, significantly dilated vena cava inferior - 36 mm in diameter. Significantly enlarged spleen 164/70 mm, vena lienalis in hilus - dilated - diameter 12 mm. Kidneys with double sizes: left 135/70 mm, right 131/60 mm. Heart - large pericardial effusion in front of the right ventricle - 16/31 mm, behind the left ventricle 24/38 mm. The

Figure 2. Echinococcal capsule-surgical removal.

Figure 3. Control CT of the brain.

pericardial effusion- next to the wall is visualized uneven cavity formation of dimensions 48/27 mm with uneven contours and liquid content. Myocardium - hyperechoic. Pulmonary artery dilated - 26 mm in diameter, pulmonary valve with pathological A wave.

Although the data from the previous disease created a suspicion about the possibility of a new echinococcal cyst in the pericardium, the dynamic monitoring of the status, as well as the data from the monitoring of the cardiac activity (ECG - tachyrrhythmic cardiac activity, HR 144 beats/min, semi-horizontal el. position, data for right ventricular burden) directed the diagnostic thinking towards a right-sided heart failure. Febrility and chest pain persisted regardless of antibacterial treatment. The risk of cardiac tamponade was real as pleural and pericardial effusions increased. (Figure 4 and 5)

The described status has put urgent need of a surgical intervention. Surgical drainage of 400 ml of pericardial fluid was performed. After insertion of pericardial and pleural drains, other 300 ml were evacuated. Histological examination of the material from the pericardium – showed non-specific pericarditis in the stage of the organization. A serological test of the pericardial fluid was done, resulting in EBV PSR (+). The test showed acute viral pericarditis caused by the EBV virus with additional hepatic involvement.

Two months later the patient became sick with fever, light fatigue, and shoulder pain. The data from the new clinical tests revealed a severe inflammatory process: CRP 271.7 mg / l; Rheumatoid factor 14.5 IU / ml, HLAB27 - negative result. Ultrasound examination - small pleural effusion to the left, peeling of 12 mm in an upright

Figure 4. Four-chamber shadow of the heart with huge pericardial effusion with signs of disturbed filling of the right ventricle, pretamponade.

Figure 5. Short-axis view of the heart showing a diffuse pericardial effusion in front of the right and behind the left ventricles.

position. Pericardium - minimum peeling of 3 mm - recurrence.

From the additional immunological studies: ANA - 0.14; ANA-1 immunoblot- anti-ds DNA (-) neg.; anti-nucleosome (-) neg.; anti SS-A (-) neg.; anti So-1 (-) neg.; anti-centromere B (-) neg.; anti SS-B (-) neg.; AST below 200 IU / ml.

Treatment with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and with corticosteroids at a later stage, lead to some reduction in joint syndrome. After a short time, the same complaints escalated, which resulted in adding Colchicine and Resochin to the therapy.

DISCUSSION

Cerebral echinococcosis is a rare type of space-occupying intracranial lesion during the childhood which is observed two to three times more often in children than in adults. Echinococcal larvae usually spread in a hematogenous way, forming primary echinococcal cysts located mainly in the area of blood supply of the internal carotid artery. Isolated cerebral echinococcosis is an exception.

The presented case is about a primary solitary echinococcal cyst with a significant mass effect. Despite

the large size of the cyst, it remained asymptomatic for a long time, with its first manifestation- epileptic seizures. In most cases, cerebral echinococcosis is accompanied by lesions of the lungs and the liver. As the brain tissue is softer, the echinococcal cyst in the brain grows faster than in the other organs. Thus, until it is large enough to cause symptoms, it is difficult to detect. The presence of cysts, that are too small, in other organs is difficult to be detected by clinical and imaging studies. Some of these small cysts cannot even be detected for 20-30 years after the diagnosis of hydatid disease. It should be considered that the immune system can inhibit larval growth in other organs and systems except the CNS (Erashin et al., 1993; Farid and Farideh, 2008; Ma et al., 2012).

The presence of persistent fetal communication may explain why primary cerebral echinococcosis is more common during the childhood.

Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis is the most common connective tissue disease among children (Brewer et al., 2002; Prakken et al., 2011; Luca and Feldman, 2013). The onset of the disease may be as early as 6 months of age, but it is the highest in the first three years from the next peak to the age of 9. There are three potential causes of this serious illness:

- Autoimmune
- Immunogenic
- Influence of the environmental factors

The clinical symptoms confirming the diagnosis consist of:

1. Morning stiffness.
2. Rheumatoid rash.
3. Febris intermittens.
4. Pericarditis.
5. Chronic uveitis.
6. Rheumatoid nodules.
7. Cervical spondylitis.
8. Tenosynovitis.
9. ANA
10. Rheumatoid factor.

The forms of juvenile idiopathic rheumatoid arthritis could be:

1. Systemic polyarticular RF (+)
2. Polyarticular RF (-)
3. Oligoarticular

Persistent

Extended

Psoriatic arthritis

Enthesitis - associated arthritis

The systemic form of rheumatoid arthritis is observed in 10 of 20% of patients. The clinical symptoms are fever, rash, lymphadenopathy, hepatosplenomegaly, pericarditis, pleuritis. Arthritis can be absent for years, but uveitis is often missing (Luca and Feldman, 2013).

The clinical evolution in our patient fits into the systemic form of rheumatoid arthritis. The short-term effect of the treatment given is a predictor of aggressive

ongoing of the disease in the future (Feldman et al., 1996).

What are the treatment options in the future?

We are going to step on the following therapeutic scheme:

- Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs
- Intra-joint steroids
- Sulfasalazine
- Hydroxychloroquine-OH-chlorogmine (Plaquenil)
- Auranofin
- Methotrexate
- IM Gold
- D-penicillamine
- Etanercept
- Azathioprine
- Cyclophosphamide
- Cyclosporine
- Enbrel
- Infliximab
- Remicade
- Adalimumab

Currently, the avant-garde options in rheumatoid arthritis' treatment include the administration of tumorous TNF- α (Woo, 2002; Burgos-Vargas and Laxer, 2005).

Adalimumab is a TNF inhibitor and it is extremely effective in patients who are not responding to treatment with Methotrexate.

The use of Kineret, Anakinra (IL-1 receptor antagonist) significantly reduces joint damage.

The new therapeutic options consist of: (Prince et al., 2007; Schmeling et al., 2014; Stoll and Cron, 2014).

- Anti-T cell therapy
- Abatacept(a monoclonal antibody against CT A₄Ig(Cytotoxic T-lymphocytic anti-gene 4))
- Anti-B cell therapy
- Rituximab
- Leukotriene and other anti-inflammatory mediators
- Tolerance induction
- Peptide analog therapy

CONCLUSIONS

In pediatric practice, clinical cases with the clinical manifestation of more than one nosological units are becoming more and more common. In addition, the oligosymptomatic manifestation of well-known "old diseases" is becoming more and more common, but with an unusual clinical manifestation. Thus, therapeutic influence requires flexibility and the use of new treatment options, even without strong evidence of their effectiveness in treating children. In conclusion, the complexity of success in diagnostic, clinical, and therapeutic behaviors requires multi-disciplinary team actions.

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